

**STORIES IN THE AGE OF AUTOMATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL
STUDY ON THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON
STUDENTS' WRITING**

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Stories in the Age of Automation: A Phenomenological Study on the Role of Artificial Intelligence on Students' Writing

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Abstract

As automation becomes increasingly integrated into educational settings, understanding its role in shaping students' writing experiences is crucial. The goal of this qualitative phenomenological research was to explore the lived experiences, motivations, role of AI in students' writing, influence of AI on the learning process, and insights in using AI writing tools of the senior high school students of Monkayo National High School. There were 10 participants in this study who were selected through snowball sampling. An in-depth interview was used to gather the information needed. The findings revealed the potentials and pitfalls of AI in developing the students' writing skills. Most of the participants have seen AI's advantages, like completing the writing tasks easily, which meets the deadline, making good-quality outputs adhering to the technicalities of grammar, improving academic achievements, and gaining knowledge about writing. However, there are also some drawbacks, like students becoming indolent and AI dependent; AI diminishes one's critical thinking skills; AI gives inaccurate information; there is a limitation on usage; it is inaccessible when offline; and it is bad for one's health. Nevertheless, the role of AI in students' writing processes is significant. Its effectiveness and efficiency cannot be denied, but it should be used in moderation. Hence, incorporating AI in learning should be guided by strategies that balance its benefits with the need to maintain creative and critical thinking in students' writing. Educators should use AI as a tool to enhance, not replace, human creativity. This approach ensures that while students benefit from AI's strengths, they continue to develop their originality and critical thinking skills in writing.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence writing tools, lived experiences, motivations, role of ai to students' writing*

Introduction

Introducing different online applications earns different reactions, especially in the academe. The emergence of AI has garnered both praise and skepticism because its accessibility may cause convenience among the students but may also encourage dependence. However, despite the notion that it disrupts students' critical thinking skills, many students still use AI as their aid, especially in their writing.

In Indonesia, a study proved the effectiveness of using Artificial Intelligence technology in an Academic Writing Class. According to Utami et al. (2023), the features of AI-based learning tools have eventually made writing an academic paper easier. Majority of the Indonesian secondary students have seen the significance, brevity, and attitude of using AI technology in their writing classes favorably. However, some studies also show that AI may hinder people's growth, skills, and intellectual development over time as they become over-reliant on what the AI can do (Chan & Hu, 2023). According to Warschauer et al. (2023), relying too much on Generative AI tools could compromise students' sincere efforts to improve their writing skills.

Furthermore, using AI might also lead to the loss of academic integrity. According to the study conducted by Ventayen (2023), it was found out that half of the students from Pangasinan State University, Lingayen Campus, are prone to cheating and might use an AI tool like ChatGPT to create content for their submissions, which could jeopardize the integrity of the educational system. Nevertheless, some students also regard ChatGPT as a helpful resource and a technology innovation.

Additionally, a study conducted by Eslit (2023) of the students and teachers of St. Michael's College, Iligan City, Philippines, shows how the participants emphasize the role that AI technologies play as facilitators in language learning lends support to the practical concerns surrounding AI integration. This shows how artificial intelligence (AI) technologies help people learn languages by giving them more opportunities to practice. This could incorporate functions like pronunciation feedback, correction, and interactive language exercises to create a more engaging learning environment.

The Secondary Teachers in Monkayo District have observed an increasing trend of students using artificial intelligence (AI), especially in writing assignments. The students depend more on AI for different parts of writing, like content generation and composition refinement. Mostly, they use AI writing tools like QuillBot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT to complete their written tasks. While acknowledging the convenience and efficiency of AI-powered writing tools, teachers have expressed concerns about students' reliance on AI and the need to understand its underlying reasons and implications.

While the prevalence of AI utilization is evident, the researcher has yet to find any existing research delving into why students adopt AI tools and the specific roles these technologies play in their writing processes. It is essential to clearly understand the purpose and process of AI in writing to develop effective and balanced educational practices that incorporate AI tools in the learning environment.

This study aimed to bridge the knowledge gap by understanding how students use AI writing tools. It was helpful to examine the

students' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights regarding using AI writing tools and their role in their writing skills in order to help educators, legislators, and developers optimize AI tools to improve students' writing experiences not only in Monkayo District and other regions but also globally.

Research Questions

In dealing into students' experiences with artificial intelligence (AI) in the context of writing, this phenomenological study addressed the following fundamental research questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the Senior High School students in using AI writing tools?
2. What are the motivations of the Senior High School students in using AI writing tools?
3. What are the roles of AI in the Senior High School Students' writing?
4. What are the influences of AI on the learning process of Senior High School Students?
5. What are the insights of the Senior High School Students into using AI writing tools?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative, phenomenological design approach to explore how students at SHS utilized AI technology to complete their writing assignments. Through in-depth interviews, the study sought to gain a profound comprehension of students' thoughts, feelings, and understanding regarding their attitudes and experiences with AI writing tools. This approach facilitated a comprehensive and detailed analysis of how students engaged with and perceived AI writing tools, capturing the intricate and personal aspects of their experiences. Moreover, the study's conclusions provided valuable insights for educators and policymakers regarding the advantages and obstacles of incorporating AI in educational environments, potentially offering guidance for developing more effective teaching techniques and AI tool integration to improve student's writing abilities and academic achievements.

Snowball sampling was chosen as it allowed us to reach students who may not readily admit to using AI writing tools. By starting with a few known users and asking them to recommend others, we gained access to a wider network of students with relevant experiences. We acknowledge that snowball sampling can lead to bias, as participants suggest others within their network. To mitigate this, we ensured our sample included students from various academic years and backgrounds.

Participants

The participants were selected through snowball sampling, a method intended to reach particular target groups. Initial participants were identified and interviewed, and they subsequently referred other students who met the study's criteria, ensuring a diverse and comprehensive sample. The inclusion criteria for this study include participants who are currently enrolled in Grades 11 or 12 in the academic year 2023-2024, who are both performing and non-performing students in different strands, and most importantly, who have used AI technologies for writing assignments. As a result of these participants' recommendations of other qualified contacts, the pool of possible participants grows.

The study conducted interviews with 10 senior high school students from Monkayo National High School, also known as Senior High School. There were 6 Grade 11 students and 4 Grade 12 students. Five are from GAS, two from the STEM strand, two from the ABM strand, and one from the HUMSS strand. Additionally, five of them consistently received "With Honors" every semester, while the remaining five were average students. These participants mentioned using AI writing tools like text generators, grammar checks, and plagiarism detectors.

The study's story is significantly shaped by the experiences and viewpoints of these participants, offering profound insights about AI's function in student writing. Their willingness to share their experiences will highlight the significance of looking at human experiences in the era of automation and shed light on the complicated link between AI and education.

Procedure

The data for the phenomenological study was collected through an in-depth interview (IDI). Before conducting the interview, the researcher had secured an Endorsement Letter from the Graduate Studies School Office and had complied with the requirements of the Ethics Review Committee (ERC). After the ERC had conducted its thorough review, they issued a Certificate of Exemption indicating that the study posed minimal risk for the participants. With this note, the researcher created an interview guide listing all the critical questions related to the study. This was done to ensure a methodical and targeted approach to data collection.

The selected participants of the study were under the supervision of the Department of Education (DepEd), so the researcher sent a letter to the Superintendent of Schools of Davao de Oro, and the Principal of Monkayo National High School – Senior High School requesting permission to conduct the study at the selected school. After permission was granted, the researcher provided parent consent first and then informed consent to participants, testifying that they agreed to take part in an IDI. The open-ended nature of our interview questions encouraged participants to tell their unique stories, allowing us to capture the details of their interactions using AI-powered writing support tools. The researcher also asked the participants for permission to record during the interview.

This comprehensive data collection process aimed to provide a holistic understanding of the impact of AI on student writing from the perspective of those who work directly with AI writing tools. In this endeavor, ethical considerations and informed consent were taken into account to protect the welfare and confidentiality of participants at every step of the research journey.

Data Analysis

Data analysis for a phenomenological study involves carefully and methodically processing the lived experiences of participants. Following the IDI data collection from the participants, the data analysis took place. Thematic analysis was used to organize the collected data. According to Dawadi (2020), thematic analysis was used to look for themes that can summarize the stories found in the reports of datasets.

First, the researcher first transcribed and thoroughly examined the collected data, which consisted of textual materials such as observation notes, interview transcripts, or other materials such as recordings. The literal answers in Bisaya dialect were translated into English to combine the ideas efficiently.

After transcribing and translating, it was then the time to code the collected data. The arrangement of the shared codes ultimately created a common idea and theme. Codes and themes are continually compared and improved in this iterative process until a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences is achieved.

Ethical Considerations

In every area of research, ethical issues were crucial. The topic became increasingly important in qualitative research, especially when the participants were members of vulnerable groups (Arifin, 2018). Since the selected participants in this study were SHS students who were still considering how to use technologies such as AI in their studies, the researcher ensured that their rights and well-being as participants were protected. The researcher also sought permission from the Department of Education – Davao de Oro School Division under the direction of the School Division Head to conduct the study.

In addition, the researcher made it a point to provide participants with parent consent, for their parents, as well as an informed consent, which clearly informed them about the purpose of this study and the procedures and identified possible consequences. Participants were free to participate or decline. If they refused to participate or withdrew during the conduct of the study, the researcher assured that this had no impact on their academic performance.

For participants who volunteered, the researcher protected their identities of the throughout the recruitment and dissemination process. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were maintained by not revealing their names but simply assigning them codes. Responses were kept confidential and respected to promote clear and honest research reporting without misleading participants or those involved in this study.

Results and Discussion

This section provides an overview of the discussions, conclusions, and recommendations derived from a study that sought to characterize the experiences of Senior High School (SHS) students in utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) and its role on their writing abilities. The research was carried out in Monkayo National High School-Senior High School, located in the Monkayo West District, within the Division of Davao de Oro.

10 SHS students in the academic year 2023-2024 participated in the study. The researcher identified them using a snowball sampling method, which relied on the participants' referrals while also adhering to specific criteria such as their academic standing, strands, and whether they were currently using AI. They were the informants for the in-depth interview, as well as the sources of information and data for the phenomenon under study.

The researcher used a qualitative phenomenological research design because this study required a thorough investigation and in accordance with reliability and transferability concerns in qualitative investigations. The researcher used one-on-one interviews to carry out a thorough investigation in order to achieve this. In-depth interviews were used in this study to help the researcher understand and delve deeper into the viewpoints of the research participants.

The interview guide's research questions and their respective order dictated the presentation order for this chapter. The talks were presented in five sections: a) the students' experiences; b) their motivations; c) the role of AI in their writing; d) the influence of AI on their learning process; and e) their insights into employing AI writing tools. The study's recurring themes, which were supported by relevant research and literature, were emphasized in the discussion part.

The structured themes and emerging themes within them provided a basis for expanding the discussion of the results in this study. Each theme was carefully reviewed and assessed to determine its alignment with the underlying literature and studies.

AI Writing Tools Used to Complete Writing Tasks. The emerging themes in this structured theme are ChatGPT, Cici, Quillbot, School Hack, Google Bard, and Character AI/Perplexity AI. These were the most common AI writing tools that the students are engaging with.

The findings revealed that most of the participants embrace ChatGPT and other AI writing tools due to their capacity to simplify and speed up the writing process. Accordingly, these technologies have greatly alleviated their academic pressure, enabling students to do tasks more efficiently and with reduced anxiety. A significant number of students have reported that the prompt feedback on grammar and vocabulary offered by AI technologies has proven to be quite advantageous in enhancing the standard of their work. Su and Yang's (2023) research showcases how generative AI, using ChatGPT, enhances education by making learning individualized and interactive, thereby enhancing student engagement and participation.

Another AI writing tool used by the participants is Cici. Students valued this AI system for its ability to clarify and provide explanations. In addition, Cici's user-friendly interface and interactive features improve users' knowledge of complex concepts, making it a highly recommended choice for anyone seeking a deeper mastery of their writing topics. Research suggests that utilizing an AI-driven writing assistant such as Cici can enhance students' overall writing proficiency, enhance their ability to generate ideas, and improve the organization of their thoughts (Chen and Wei, 2021).

Quillbot is used by certain individuals for duties such as summarizing, paraphrasing, and grammatical checking in essays. This AI tool is highly advantageous for tackling the complex elements of writing. The powerful mechanisms and accessible interface improve the clarity, syntactic organization, and grammatical accuracy. Participants found that Quillbot not only accelerates the writing process but also improves their capacity to produce polished and complete work. The results are consistent with the research conducted by Syahnaz & Fithriani (2023), which states that QuillBot has three advantages. Firstly, it aids in enhancing the content or argument. Secondly, it reduces grammatical errors. Lastly, it improves the language used in their writings.

Furthermore, Study Hack, another widely-used AI writing tool, aids users in acquiring a more profound comprehension of their subjects. This illustrates that AI tools have a dual focus on strengthening writing skills and improving the overall learning process. Study Hack enhances users' educational experience by offering deep understanding and promoting analytical thinking, enabling them to deeply interact with their subjects. *The result agrees to Imran and Almusharraf (2023) that AI tools can offers opportunities for improvement, educators need to address concerns regarding academic integrity, originality, and assessment methods. One participant applied Google Bard as an artificial intelligence tool to improve their writing abilities. Responding to inquiries, this generative artificial intelligence completes text-based tasks including content creation, summarizing, and replying. Particularly in academic writing and language acquisition, the introduction of AI tools like Google Bard has also fundamentally altered students' writing practices (Moore et al., 2016; Peters and Cadieux, 2019). These resources help with the technical elements of writing as well as create a more participatory and interesting classroom.*

Lastly, Character AI and Perplexity AI were used by a participant for referencing in research purposes. These AI-powered tools are making the research process more efficient and accurate, from finding sources to analyzing data (Rathinasabapathy et al., 2023). By automating routine tasks and providing advanced data analysis capabilities, these tools allow researchers to focus on critical thinking and interpretation. This leads to more comprehensive and insightful research outcomes, highlighting the transformative impact of AI on academic and professional research practices.

Describing Experiences Using AI Writing Tools. Describing Experiences Using AI Writing Tools. This structured theme elicited six emerging themes: Making Study/Task Easy, Amazed, Very Helpful, Shortcut in Making Tasks, Good and Positive to Use, and Worth it but Difficult to Understand. According to the findings, the majority of the informants stated that AI writing tools brought so many benefits for them as students. These technologies optimized their study processes, simplifying tasks and making them more manageable. The remarkable abilities of AI left many in awe, as they found it highly beneficial in enhancing the efficiency of project execution. While certain individuals perceived it as a simple expedient for accomplishing tasks, others acknowledged its overall beneficial influence. Nevertheless, some participants acknowledged that, despite its benefits, comprehending and effectively utilizing the technology could present difficulties.

Another important theme that came up was how students have found AI to make their work easy. The majority of the people who spoke said that AIs are very helpful for understanding and solving complicated questions, giving faster, more useful results. AI helps students with their essay assignments by giving them useful information, creating material, suggesting ways to make things better, and even helping with formatting and citing. AI tools also often give immediate feedback, which helps students improve their work quickly. Students found it easier to complete the assignments because of its capacity to give them immediate, helpful feedback (Robert et al., 2024).

Since artificial intelligence brought several tools that would help students, it was certain that the newly created technology was going to amaze and leave a lasting effect on them. The user would just leave a command, and out of nowhere a produced answer would show above expectations. This amazing interface with artificial intelligence not only makes tasks easier but also induces wonder and admiration of its capabilities. According to Serrano et al. (2018), AI helps students create more effective forms of reflection and analyze the learning data it provides, making it more accessible and amazing.

In addition, participants viewed AI as both very helpful and a shortcut for completing tasks due to its ability to produce output easily and quickly, thereby increasing productivity. Haristiani (2019) found that students are drawn to chatbots because they can use them anywhere, at any time. This accessibility and efficiency make AI tools particularly attractive for students looking to manage their

workloads more effectively. Its capacity to rapidly analyze information and generate solutions has altered the ease with which students complete writing assignments

Likewise, AI could assist them in understanding the theoretical concepts, teach them the necessary vocabulary and grammar, and guide them through the writing process (Sumakul et al., 2021). This would make AI good and positive to use in the lives of the students especially in writing. One participant even shared how AI corrected their grammar and spelling, demonstrating its positive impact on their academic endeavors. This illustrates the practicality and effectiveness of integrating AI into students' lives, enhancing their learning experience and academic performance.

Despite its benefits, AI still has room for improvement due to occasional shortcomings. Another theme is that while AI is worth it but difficult to understand. It offers benefits in various areas but may use complex language in responses, posing challenges for some users. Kumar's (2023) study on AI-generated responses to academic writing revealed improper references and a lack of personal viewpoints. This underscores AI's inability to replicate essential human qualities like subjective experiences and feelings, which can limit its suitability in certain cases. This is why students will have a difficulty understanding some generated answers sometimes.

Frequency of Using AI Writing Tools. The responses elicited three emerging themes: Sometimes if Needed, Most Often, and Always. Most participants shared that they turn to AI mainly to speed up task submission, especially for subjects that require precise language use and clarification. This reliance on AI for urgent tasks shows how helpful it is in meeting tight deadlines and handling complex language challenges. It highlights the practical benefits of AI in their academic lives, making it an essential tool for managing the pressures of their coursework.

Yustiana et al. (2024) examine the frequency of AI tool use in EFL writing classes for higher education, exploring how these tools impact teaching and learning. Their focus on utilization frequency contributes to understanding how technology can improve writing skills in language education. This research sheds light on the practical implications and challenges of integrating AI into EFL writing instruction, providing valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and researchers in the field.

The findings also indicated that certain participants wholeheartedly adopt AI and utilize it more often. They are incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) into their study routines by utilizing it for tasks such as essay composition, grammar verification, and understanding complex subjects. This showcases the capacity of AI to revolutionize education and enhance academic achievement. Alharbi (2023) corroborates this discovery, stating that AI tools are invaluable to writers in both the pre-writing and post-writing stages. These tools provide students with sentence completion suggestions and text generation that closely resemble human-like output.

Furthermore, among the individuals who effectively control their use of AI, one individual stated that he continuously relies on AI for every writing assignment. Anggoro (2019) found that technology users expect to derive utility from executing tasks when they have a purpose and can be used to accomplish specific objectives, similar to how AI authoring tool's function. This is the reason he consistently utilizes AI, as it significantly enhances his academic performance.

Challenges Encountered When Using AI Writing tools. Five key themes emerged from the responses. These were problems with not giving an accurate answer, none, no internet connection, limitations of usage, and being difficult to understand. The study's results revealed that despite the students' positive experiences, they still face certain challenges.

One common challenge that the students encountered was the AI's inability to provide accurate answers. As they stated, the generated responses differ significantly from their requirements, and some appear to be inaccurate upon further verification on other websites. Nevertheless, their inclination to visit diminished when inaccurate information was included, particularly if it was more noticeable or within the same category (Kim et al., 2023). The AI's unreliability weakened trust among students, prompting them to return to conventional approaches for research and learning. Although the promise of AI tools to boost productivity is acknowledged, the presence of accuracy issues highlights the necessity for ongoing enhancement of AI programs.

Conversely, several participants said they had no trouble integrating AI into their research and had a smooth experience doing so. This is consistent with Chen et al.'s (2022) research, which found that AI helps students understand foundational material in a responsive, interactive, and private way. These chatbots have the potential to be highly effective conversational learning systems that teach basic concepts and distribute educational materials in an engaging and responsive manner.

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has the capacity to greatly improve learning outcomes; nevertheless, its advantages are not equally attainable for all students because there are some students who do not always have a sufficient internet connection. This disparity is especially noticeable for students living in distant or economically challenged regions. Mozumder et al. (2023) emphasized that children in these areas may encounter difficulties in obtaining AI resources, thus increasing the current gap in educational outcomes. The use of high-speed internet and modern digital devices, which depend on internet connectivity for immediate analysis and suggestions, worsens this inequality which make this situation a challenge for the users.

The participants also face limitations when using AI. Non-premium AI technologies restrict students' capabilities and resources. Some students may find AI tools less effective due to their limited access to advanced features, exacerbating the educational gap. The inaccessible use of AI could limit their ability to think creatively and independently (Johinke et al., 2023).

Lastly, many students often struggle to understand AI answers due to their complex language or lack of context. This can make it harder for them to fully use these technologically advanced instruments. Also, AI tools might not fully understand the variety and complexity of human emotion and language, which could lead to suggestions that are wrong or inappropriate in some cases (Haleem et al., 2022).

Ways Used to Address the Challenges Encountered Using AI Writing Tools. The emerging themes were Be Patient, Repeating the Question to AI, Giving AI the Specific Question, Understanding the Answer Given, Self-Reliance, and Verify to Other Website. The findings revealed that the informants used different techniques to cope with the challenges they experienced. Dealing with challenges presented by artificial intelligence necessitates that user be more patient, as these instruments are tools rather than substitutes for human judgment and critical thinking. This flexible strategy helps students minimize the drawbacks of artificial intelligence and enhance its advantages.

Patience is truly be given an importance in using AI just like what a certain participant said, it is us who need its service. Actually, Eryilmaz & Basal (2024) highlighted that developing strategies to maintain the use of a certain technology depends on patience. They must so be patient if they want to really grasp how it works. It provides pupils with the tools they need to approach challenges methodically, handle disappointments, and be receptive to little stages of learning. This prepares students for more successful academics and careers in artificial intelligence.

Another set of strategies that the students employed whenever the AI did not get the user's wanted information was to repeat the question to the AI and give specific questions. These are done by the participants to improve their chances of getting a more accurate and useful answer related to their writing tasks. This technique demonstrates the importance of perseverance and flexibility when utilizing AI technologies, allowing students to take full advantage of the technology's possibilities. Moreover, we can further improve the accuracy of the system by strategically employing repetition and refraining from using prompts that allow for multiple interpretations (Vidhani, 2024).

Understanding the answers given by AI is crucial for establishing efficient coping mechanisms. This would necessitate collaboration with AI tools and transforming obstacles into opportunities for personal growth. The difficulty in understanding the answers has the potential to raise risks, such as misunderstandings (Popenici & Kerr, 2017; Reiss, 2021). A thorough understanding of AI responses not only helps to avoid these traps, but also improves students' capacity to successfully utilize AI, resulting in improved learning outcomes and more significant academic accomplishments.

In addition, participants noted that when AI is not accessible, one strategy they use is to work on the writing task independently or to have self-reliance. Students are still capable of producing high-quality outputs by applying their acquired knowledge. The desired outcome should be to empower people to recognize the quality of AI advice and act upon it to make better decisions, rather than relying solely on it (Schemmer et al., 2022). This strategy emphasizes the importance of self-reliance and strengthens the abilities and understanding gained through traditional learning methods, ensuring that students maintain their ability to adjust and find solutions even without the help of AI.

Additionally, verifying the generated answers to other websites was done by the students to ensure that the information given is valid and reliable. It is also very important to conduct regular monitoring and assessment of AI activities for identifying areas that require improvement (Estrellado and Miranda, 2023). The act of cross-referencing serves two purposes: verifying the AI's responses for accuracy and fostering critical thinking and comprehensive research abilities in students.

Motivation in Using AI Writing Tools in Academic Work. After a thorough analysis about their motivations in using AI, the following emergent themes are generated and these are the following: Getting Quick Answers, For Good Writing Outputs, Meeting Deadlines, Motivated by Indolence, To Get Good Grades, Enhancing English Skills, and Recommended by Classmates.

The primary motivation for students to interact with AI is its capacity to provide prompt responses. The participants indicated that AI had facilitated their information management. The students' motivation and interest of using AI have been raised as it greatly influences their learning outcomes (Muñoz et al., 2023). The prompt response and support provided by AI technologies motivate students to actively participate in their academic pursuits, resulting in enhanced understanding and long-term retention of knowledge.

The second emerged motivation is the ability of the AI to produce good writing outputs. It improves students writing abilities by structuring material, enhancing grammar, and refining style. According to reports, the AI chatbot generated coherent and informative content (Salido, 2023). This feature not only assists students in producing well-organized essays and reports but also functions as an educational resource, offering instant grammar corrections and creative recommendations.

Third, participants want to finish their writing assignments on time. Using AI software for writing helps meet tight deadlines. AI-generated material, draft refinement, and feedback accelerate the writing process. This efficiency helps students' study and manage their time. AI can minimize deadline stress and anxiety, making school more pleasant and productive. According to Holmes et al. (2019), AI helps in increasing students' cognition through its unique characteristics, including fast data collection, analysis, and translation into meaningful insights and actions, which makes it more useful for meeting deadlines.

Indolence is the driving force of the students motivation, which is the fourth topic that developed. There are a considerable number of students who experience periodic difficulties in their academic pursuits. These difficulties include issues such as procrastination, as well as a perceived lack of enthusiasm and ambition. The findings of Ahmad et al. (2023), which demonstrate that artificial intelligence has a major impact on the loss of human decision-making and renders humans lazy, are supported by this evidence.

A significant number of students set obtaining high grades as their primary objective, which serves as the fifth motivation why they are using AI. One of the primary motivations for students to utilize AI writing tools is their desire to improve academic performance. This is a primary incentive for the participants. Salido (2023) then supported this claim as her study indicated that artificial intelligence has the capacity to transform education by enabling personalized and adaptable educational experiences for students, leading to improved academic performance and overall comprehension.

Among the students' motivations for embracing AI is its capacity to improve their English skills, especially in writing. Everybody needs this highly essential ability since it may be applied in the actual world and in any other facet of schooling. Marzuki et al. (2023) revealed AI writing tools had an advantageous effect on the writing quality of their students, particularly those their content and structure.

As a last point, the students are employing AI since they are affected by their fellow students The environment that surrounds an individual has a considerable impact on the level of motivation that they have to use artificial intelligence (Muñoz et al., 2023).

Reasons for Using AI writing tools. Three themes emerged from the study, explaining why students engage with AI: making writing tasks easier, not being smart, and finding apps helpful. There may be different reasons, but one thing is common: the AI is making a difference by making the writing tasks easier to complete.

According to Ginting et al. (2023), students can efficiently examine and choose suitable grammatical structures, significantly diminishing the time needed to finish their final assignments by utilizing AI-driven writing tools. AI convinces students to use it because it simplifies their tasks. In fact, one participant stated that utilizing AI is a big help in completing their Practical Research output. He was able to maintain his eagerness to finish the task because there was AI present on his back. Its convenience is incomparable according to another informant.

Artificial intelligence can also help individuals who doubt their intelligence. An additional reason for using AI is that it can help people overcome self-doubt and study more by providing quick comments, clear explanations, and meticulous recommendations. Artificial intelligence supports learning, making it less scary and more accessible, creating a more inclusive learning environment where any student may succeed. AI solutions have the potential to boost a writer's confidence by serving as a supportive companion during the writing process (Washington, 2023).

Overall, the reason for using AI is that the students found AI-generated applications helpful in every aspect of writing. It is useful for creating various writing tasks, such as essays and reports. It enhances the user's grammar and may improve their vocabulary. In short, it has already played a significant role in students' lives. According to Kim and Cho (2023), a number of students had the notion that artificial intelligence may be a helpful tool that would assist them in completing the sketching project in a more efficient manner.

Benefits AI Writing Tools Bring to Writing and Learning Process. The responses revealed three emerging themes that signify the students' presumed benefits of AI to their writing and learning process. These are the three themes: gaining knowledge about writing, being a bit helpful, and making studying easy.

The main benefit that students realized is that gaining knowledge about writing. Students think artificial intelligence helps them grasp writing styles and tactics. Artificial intelligence can help students enhance their writing and communication skills by advising on essay format, grammar, and style. Liu et al. (2023) found that students who employed artificial intelligence (AI) on an online learning system, such as ChatGPT, reported a higher level of involvement in their studies. Furthermore, many of these students expressed delight in interacting with the program.

The second theme proves that AI is indeed extremely useful as providing a considerable number of benefits. It helps them expand their vocabulary and provides answers to the questions they face when writing. Gayed et al. (2022) investigated the impact of artificial intelligence writing tools on students' vocabulary and explored potential enhancements, which proved that it really improves their vocabulary. It also the participants in every written task.

The last advantage is the simplicity of difficult assignments, thus making the study easy. AI can clearly explain difficult ideas, efficiently arrange data, and divide tough ideas into more reasonable pieces. AI simplifies the very complicated problems of human existence (Fitria, 2021). This gives students more confidence and ease in tackling difficult topics. AI can also customize learning opportunities by adjusting to particular student requirements and offering customized help targeted to particular areas of challenge.

Ways in which AI Assist in Writing Assignments or Activities. This structured theme elicited three emerging themes: Providing Needed Answers, Provide Assistance for Answers, and Guidance in Grammar and Punctuations. According to the findings, the majority of the informants stated that AI provides needed answers. Whenever they are assigned for a writing task, AI is there to give them answers.

Writing benefits greatly from artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence provides needed answers to various writing tasks within a short timeframe. AI offers inspiration and fresh ideas to enhance your writing. AI offers an automated assistant to facilitate your writing, especially during critical moments. Participants would agree that they were not struggling anymore to finish tasks because AI is readily available. It helps students improve their work's organization by giving them immediate feedback and suggestions for moving phrases and paragraphs (Chang et al., 2021).

Another major subject that pertains to how artificial intelligence helps students with their writing assignments is the provision of assistance for answers. Artificial intelligence is valuable in many different fields, particularly in the field of education. Students frequently struggle to generate works that have logical flow and coherence, according to Bowen and Thomas (2020), who argue that concept structure is an essential component of writing in a second language. Providing suggestions, coming up with new ideas, and polishing the content are all ways in which artificial intelligence may be of great assistance with creative or writing endeavors. When a person is experiencing difficulty writing any written works, artificial intelligence can be of assistance to them.

Additionally, AI offers students assistance with grammar and punctuation, which is becoming increasingly important. Marzuki et al. (2023) demonstrated in their research that artificial intelligence considerably improved the quality of writing produced by students. These software applications make use of sophisticated methods to identify common errors in grammar, punctuation, and syntax, and they provide recommendations to improve the clarity and style of the writing. The participants have mentioned that they rely on the use of AI when it comes to polishing their grammar and punctuations.

Ways in which AI helps Identify and Address Areas for Improvement in Writing. There are different ways as to how AI assists the students in identifying and addressing the areas of improvement in their writing. In this structured theme, there emerged three topics: Getting Knowledge in Sentence Construction, and Improving Writing.

The primary theme emerged is to get the knowledge in sentence construction. This process revealed as mostly the learning of knowledge in sentence building. Receiving comments helps students understand how to create logical and cohesive sentence. By improving their capacity to clearly and successfully express ideas, this not only increases their writing abilities but also helps them to achieve generally in academics. According to Tambunan et al. (2022), artificial intelligence provides context-specific recommendations for improvements that help students avoid typical errors and simplify their writing especially in sentence construction.

Correcting wrong essays is another theme that emerged in how they address their weaknesses in writing with the use of AI. Discussions often revolve around how AI addresses its shortcomings in writing. This capability allows students to pinpoint particular areas in their writing that need development. This increased awareness enables individuals to adopt a proactive approach in their educational endeavors, enabling them to identify specific areas of weakness and progressively develop stronger and more polished writing skills. According to Marzuki et al. (2023), artificial intelligence has algorithms that can recognize common faults in syntax and grammar which is useful in making essays.

The third emerging theme is AI's ability to improve writing. Kurniati and Fithriani (2021) demonstrated that AI assisted in developing better paraphrasing skills and other writing technicalities. Students can reword their sentences to be more expressive and minimize repetition, which will increase their vocabulary and stylistic diversity. Students can use them as a great tool to test out various writing concepts and styles. Gayed et al. (2022) investigated the impact of AI writing tools on student vocabulary usage and enhancement.

Describing Overall Experience with AI-based Writing Tools. The responses elicited five emerging themes: not time-consuming, easy and helpful, very fascinating, rating as satisfied, and a great and positive experience. The findings revealed that their overall experience has been positive and used it as it is not time consuming.

As a result of the fact that AI is an automated technology, its reaction to each and every instruction does not require a lot of time. Using artificial intelligence to write has altered the way in which students complete their written assignments, allowing them to complete them more quickly. AI is the technique whereby machines can learn and comprehend reason similar to human understanding. Said to be able to simplify very complicated human existence is this technology (Fitria, 2021).

Also, students would agree for the capability of AI to be easy and helpful to use. Salido (2023) found that AI writing tools help learners understand complex ideas and improve their performance in several subjects. AI tools make learning easier by reducing complicated ideas and delivering customized explanations. Students gain confidence in tough subjects and a deeper comprehension and retention of knowledge. AI writing tools are vital to their academic improvement and performance.

According to Serrano et al. (2018), AI makes data analysis and reflection more fascination and accessible for students. AI is very fascinating as it can customize instructional information to individual learning styles to improve comprehension and retention. It identifies knowledge gaps and suggests resources to fill them, improving learning. Students who collaborate with experts and classmates using AI-driven technology can create a community of practice and continual improvement.

Furthermore, for some of the participants, artificial intelligence only provides a fair level of satisfaction to the learning process of the pupils. They were confronted with both the benefits and the drawbacks of utilizing AI. Additionally, for certain participants, the learning process of the students is only moderately satisfying as induced by artificial intelligence. It facilitates personalized and adaptable

educational opportunities by offering students customized feedback and information that aligns with their individual learning preferences and requirements (Robert et al., 2024).

Generally, the overall experience of the students is great and positive. AI tools greatly improve the learning process for students since they offer particular answers and efficient solutions for issues. As AI catered to personal needs can improve a writer's self-perception and performance (Gao et al., 2021). These instruments guarantee that every student gets the appropriate degree of challenge and assistance by providing tailored learning routes that fit to their particular requirement. Instant feedback lets students fix errors in front of them, therefore reinforcing their knowledge and increasing their confidence. AI catered to personal needs can improve a writer's self-perception and performance (Gao et al., 2021).

Perception of Impact of AI Writing Tools on Overall Learning Experience and Academic Achievements. This structured theme elicited three emerging themes: Big Help, Just Fine, and Becoming Indolent.

The findings revealed that AI is a big help for students to improve their academic grades. AI has a small impact on learning perception but a huge impact on learning achievement, according to Zheng et al. (2023). Students may not see the immediate benefits of AI tools, but the measurable consequences in grades and performance are significant. Students also discover AI tactics and techniques to improve their writing. The use of AI in education creates a supportive and dynamic learning environment that helps students succeed academically.

In addition, the participants discussed their experiences with artificial intelligence and stated that they found it acceptable because it yields satisfactory results. Users who can manage the output of AI writing assistance are more inclined to trust it, according to research by Anderson et al. (2020). As a result, the positive impact of AI on writing processes, such as improving speed, quality, and creativity, encouraged the participants to rate it just fine.

Conversely, becoming indolent is an emerging theme that significantly impacts the overall learning experience. Given the capabilities of AI, the majority of participants have already begun to rely on it. Although AI-driven enhancements can boost perceived competency, writers who rely too much on AI-generated ideas run a certain danger. This dependence may hinder the development of natural writing skills over time, therefore producing a difference between perceived and actual writing competence (Chen, 2018).

Specific Changes in Study Habits or Learning Approaches Result from the Integration of AI Writing Tools into Educational Process. This structured theme resulted in two emerging themes: Becoming Indolent and Dependent on AI, and No Changes. Either the participants have changed how they learn or they remain the same. However, most of them answered that they had become reliant on AI.

According to Hao et al. (2021), the ease of use of content generated by artificial intelligence has the potential to inhibit the development of a distinctive writing voice. This is because writers may rely on ideas generated by AI rather than experimenting with their own creative expressions. Users, such as the participants themselves, are entirely reliant on artificial intelligence due of the benefits it offers. There is a possibility that students will become unduly dependent on these tools as they grow more widespread. This could be detrimental to the development of abilities in critical thinking and independent learning strategies.

However, several participants stated that their study habits remained the same, suggesting that individual differences may exist in how AI affects study habits. Notably, their use of AI in the classroom does not impede critical thinking or creativity (Liang et al., 2021). Notwithstanding these reservations, artificial intelligence (AI) continues to have a generally favorable impact on education, creating a dynamic and encouraging learning environment that inspires students to realize their full potential and succeed academically.

Insights Gained from Using AI Writing Tools for Academic Assignments. With their usage of AI, the participants have learned so much in their experience. The following are the emerging themes that gave them realizations: Acquire Learning about Writing, AI with Advantages and Disadvantages, Use AI in Moderation, Learn Answers from AI, Not Time Consuming, AI as Potential Learning Tool, and Not to be Dependent on AI.

The primary theme is that artificial intelligence now possesses writing knowledge. One participant even noted that his writing style differs greatly. Using artificial intelligence tools for homework has given the participants a lot of writing experience. These AI tools help them understand writing styles better and offer useful direction, therefore accelerating and improving the learning process. Awada et al. (2020) claim that artificial intelligence provides outstanding organization that ensures a smooth flow of ideas, so improving the readability and forceful power of the writing. Students admire the ability of artificial intelligence technologies to excel in proofreading and editing tasks.

The second insight is that they have come to understand that AI has advantages and disadvantages. According to the findings of study conducted by Al-Tkhayneh et al. (2023), most students believe artificial intelligence can analyze an extensive amount of data, enhance task management, increase learning and personal experience, and assist in processing of personal experiences. On the other hand, some may rely too much on artificial intelligence as others have different ideas about its capacity to regulate students' conduct and direct learning. This would put the participants at the forefront of AI's advantages and disadvantages.

Thirdly, there are some who thought that AI should be used in moderation and should not be abused. Thought it would really help the participants in completing their writing assignments, they still need to stand on their own. They have to improve task management in order to process information (AI-Tkhayneh et al., 2023). The process guarantees users have control over their work and maintain their own style and style in writing. Students can actively participate in the writing process and yet employ artificial intelligence in moderation to improve efficiency and output.

Fourthly, participants have also learned about the generated answers of AI. The participant made sure that everything should be understood. Participants also now know how to evaluate responses produced by artificial intelligence. Students must interact with the material to confirm its authenticity and relevancy, so this procedure guarantees a complete knowledge of the offered material. By means of this contact with artificial intelligence, learning can be reinforced and students' active analysis and integration of knowledge guaranteed against their passive acceptance. The study by Khare et al. (2018) looked at how AI changes students' lives, especially when it comes to getting help while they are in school.

The fifth theme that surfaced is the capacity of artificial intelligence to not waste too much time processing your prompt. Its great efficiency lets quick answers for user questions possible. From user assistance to real-time data analysis, where fast information processing is vital, this efficiency is vital in many uses. AI is, according to Ginting et al. (2023), cutting the time needed to do writing assignments. By helping students more effectively manage their schoolwork, artificial intelligence frees them to concentrate on more difficult and creative facets of their education.

The sixth topic is regarding the use of artificial intelligence (AI) as a possible educational aid for students. Given that artificial intelligence is becoming increasingly prevalent in today's environment, one of the participants suggested that it may be used as a tool to enhance the learning experience of students, particularly in the area of writing. In their study, Bailey et al. (2021) discovered that the students believed the artificial intelligence was user-friendly, relevant to their learning, and assisted them in accomplishing their goals about the second language. These concepts are merely examples of how artificial intelligence writing tools offer benefits to users, particularly students. Students' use of AI writing tools can be attributed to the fact that these tools are both accessible and flexible.

Lastly, AI should also teach students not to depend on it completely. The participants have experienced some drawbacks like getting inaccurate answers. These instruments might not be able to completely reflect the diversity and complexity of human language and emotion, so recommendations that are unsuitable or erroneous in a given context could follow (Haleem et al., 2022).

Advantages of Using AI Writing Tools. The participants have seen the benefits of utilizing AI in their studies, especially in completing their writing assignments. They reported that they were able to produce well-written and organized outputs. This structured theme encompasses two emerging themes: helping students with writing skills, and writing becoming easy.

A majority of students thought that artificial intelligence really helped them to get better at writing. It offers several writing strategies, language choices, quick notes, and developmental suggestions. Artificial intelligence techniques can find grammar mistakes, change sentence construction, and raise general coherence. This quick direction encourages improved writing habits by let pupils learn and correct problems in real time. These resources helped students to acquire more writing autonomy and to improve their quality of work (Thet and Htay, 2021). The participants were able to manipulate the correct usage of grammar through the help of AI.

Using artificial intelligence has made writing tasks easier to complete, consequently simplifying students' life. The qualities of AI primarily aim to ease students' assignment pressure. The second emerging theme revolves around AI's ability to make the writing tasks easy to accomplish. According to the study by Bailey et al. (2021), the students found the AI was user-friendly, relevant to their learning, and helped them attain their second language objectives. As it is user-friendly, it was able to provide a written output in just a few seconds. The participants were able to submit assignments as promptly as possible.

Disadvantages of Using AI Writing Tools. Every new technology has certain downsides even if it offers benefits. In this study, there emerged six themes where the participants have realized. These are the following: Becoming Indolent, Not Helping One's Critical Thinking, Becoming AI Dependent, Giving Inaccurate Information, Inaccessible when Offline, and Bad for One's Health.

Becoming indolent is one of the disadvantages of AI. The participants who took part in the activity admitted to their own laziness and discussed their experiences. They have already developed into individuals who are passive, and rather than learning via the process of hard work, they choose to become dependent on it. Specifically, the findings of Ahmad et al. (2023) regarding the significant impact that artificial intelligence has had on the lowering of human decision-making and the encouragement of individual laziness.

Another emerging theme is that AI becomes unhelpful in developing one's critical thinking skills. The students' capacity for critical thinking may be harmed if they become overly dependent on AI writing tools (Iskender, 2023). This particular position was presented to address the students' problems in diminishing their critical thinking skills. In fact, one participant said that AI impedes the development of independent thought processes.

The third seen disadvantage of using AI is the tendency of the students to rely on AI. There is also the possibility of placing an excessive amount of dependence on artificial intelligence technology, which could result in students having a passive learning experience (Robert, 2024). In order to maintain meaningful relationships and to foster deeper comprehension, it is essential to strike a balance

between the employment of artificial intelligence and human education and direction. It is also said by the participants that relying on AI would also result in a decrease in self-confidence.

AI can sometimes produce inaccurate data. This leads to another theme of AI's disadvantage of giving inaccurate information. Kim et al. (2023) found that students' enthusiasm to use AI reduced when AI delivered erroneous information, especially when the inaccuracies were evident or related to established subjects. Unreliable AI made students rely more on traditional research and teaching methods. Although AI tools boost output, these accuracy issues underscore the need for continual AI system development. The participants have to be verified to make sure that the information is valid and reliable.

Moreover, AI as being inaccessible when offline was also seen by the participants. Mozumder et al. (2023) observed in their study that students that do not have access to high-speed internet or inaccessible access will have educational gap. An internet connection is necessary for many AI writing tools to provide real-time analysis and recommendations. For students who live in places with poor or no internet access, this could be problematic to access AI.

Anwar et al. (2021) discovered that chronic usage of electronic devices, including cellphones and other electronic gadgets, has a detrimental effect on one's eyesight. Given that artificial intelligence will only be utilized through the utilization of various devices, we are able to assert that excessive exposure to it will have a negative effect on our eyes.

Conclusions

The exploration into the lived experiences of Senior High School students using AI writing tools has provided valuable insights into their motivations, challenges, and perceptions. The findings reveal that students rely on AI writing tools to enhance their academic writing, driven by motivations such as efficiency, improved writing quality, and time management. Despite encountering challenges like inaccurate responses and dependency concerns, students have demonstrated resilience in addressing these obstacles, showcasing their adaptability and problem-solving skills.

The role of AI in students' writing processes is significant, with AI tools assisting in grammar checks, content generation, and citation management, making tasks easier and fostering creativity. This integration of AI has influenced students' learning experiences, facilitating faster assignment completion and aiding in identifying areas for improvement in writing. While students acknowledge the benefits of AI writing tools in enhancing their writing and learning process, they also recognize the importance of not becoming overly dependent on them, highlighting the need for a balanced approach to their use.

Although the study only focused on the replies of students from Monkayo National High School - Senior High School, Monkayo West District, Division of Davao de Oro, the following potential areas for further research are acknowledged:

First, future research may be conducted with a large scale of participants, not only the Senior High School (SHS) students but also the Junior High School (JHS) students in the Division of Davao de Oro, to understand if the SHS students have the same lived experiences as the JHS students in using AI to complete their writing tasks.

Second, as this study was done in a public secondary school. Further research could be done to explore the same phenomenon among private secondary schools to compare if there is a difference between the two sectors.

Third, future studies should investigate whether frequent use of artificial intelligence writing tools enhances or restricts students' critical thinking and creativity, thereby influencing their development. Since the participants are new to AI, it would be interesting to see the long-term effects if they had previously used AI.

Fourth, next researches may also examine how AI tools impact different groups of students, including those with various educational backgrounds and skill levels, to see if AI helps reduce or increase educational inequalities.

Fifth, future researches should also look into the ethical issues and academic honesty concerns of AI-generated content, and establish clear guidelines for responsible use, especially in determining for the teachers in checking students' output.

Finally, given students' wide acquaintance with AI, it would be good to investigate the role of instructors in navigating its incorporation. This necessitates greater inquiry, particularly into how teacher training and professional development may be tailored to successfully include AI into curriculum.

By tackling these study topics, researchers may help to establish a deeper awareness of AI's role in education, eventually shaping policies that promote both technical innovation and holistic student development.

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